

A PHENOMENOLOGICAL RESEARCH: THE TRANSITION TO HYBRID LEARNING OF PSYCHOLOGY STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 3

Pages: 266-272

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2258

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13370545

Manuscript Accepted: 07-26-2024

A Phenomenological Research: The Transition to Hybrid Learning of Psychology Students

Christian Angelo Ruiz,* Jerome Arvin Sebastian, Robert Wayne Torres, Danise Angelica G. Lacson
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The education system has sought ways to deliver quality education using different means and platforms. This study dives into the various experiences of students in hybrid learning. This study focuses on students' experiences with hybrid learning, including the difficulties they overcame, the adjustments they had to make, the lessons they learned from engaging in this type of learning that combines in-person and online classes, as well as their perceptions of their learning environment and general well-being as learners. The researchers aim to elucidate the challenges they have encountered and surpassed, and the obstacles they have adapted to achieve success during hybrid learning, which is still a rather fresh form of learning for most students and teachers alike. The study not only aims to assist in marking hybrid learning as a feasible and effective mode of learning, but also wishes to relay the difficulties students have faced and overcome, and the perceived strengths and weaknesses of the two primary modes of learning we have discussed. The researchers employed qualitative research techniques and the phenomenological approach in conducting this study. The researchers utilized purposive sampling and interviewed 10 students from NU Fairview to gather the data and understand the actual experiences of students, their preferences, their perceptions, and the things they have done during the transition to hybrid learning due to uncontrollable events like a pandemic. In the study, thematic analysis was used by the researchers to examine the interview-based data. Through this process, we were able to focus on four key themes: "Accepting the Hybrid Shift," "Hybrid Hurdles," "Beyond the Screen," and "Finding Balance." These themes covered the essence of the students' experiences, difficulties encountered as well as obstacles surmounted, perspectives, adaptations in adjustments, as well as comparisons and insights related to hybrid learning. The findings of this study satisfy and justify the research by illuminating hybrid learning's characteristics informing educators and educational institutions on how to enhance student experiences and maximize learning outcomes in this style of hybrid learning.

Keywords: *hybrid learning, online learning, face-to-face learning, social interaction*

Introduction

Education has been a heavily hit sector by the pandemic, which disrupted one of the most important aspects of human development, education. The pandemic made education hard to attain, especially due to the lack of appropriate resources and the sudden shift of the mode of learning from face-to-face classes to online classes. (Tadessee et al. 2020). This new form of learning has also called for abrupt changes in one's learning environment and how they approach their education while adjusting to the new predicament and the challenges it entails, such as a deficit in social interaction once readily available prior to the pandemic (Biwer et al. 2021).

According to Ouma (2021), online learning is advantageous due to its applications in many fields, its versatility and accessibility, and the benefit of removing the strains coming from commuting and other activities. Still, these advantages are overshadowed by many disadvantages brought upon by external factors, mainly revolving around access to the necessary resources and materials to achieve optimal functionality. In a study by Alawamleh et al., (2020), it was stated that the majority of students prefer face-to-face classes because of the problems that online classes produce, such as a lack of motivation in the online setting given its static class time, resulting in no sense of urgency or motivation and procrastination. Online learning also affects the student/teacher relationship as the knowledge and means of teaching delivered may be seen as insufficient by students (Gheres et al. 2021). Moreover, online classes may apply better to certain personality types or different types of learners. Take introverts, for example; with online classes, they are free from the shackles of pressure to participate and can think freely without fearing anything. (Study International, 2020). There is also student performance and education effectiveness to analyze when considering what mode of learning is best (Zheng et al. 2021).

Hybrid learning is an excellent mode of learning that blends in significant aspects of both online and face-to-face learning, developing a network of support for students while not being detrimental to their autonomy and promoting better learning experience (Miles et al. 2018). It is also a mode of learning that supports autonomy in a student-centered way which technology assists in which also incorporates a blend of educator-centered learning due to shifting schedules that allow for flexibility (Li et al. 2021) that then also allows for a variety of opportunities to collaborate with others which not only improves the learning environment and experiences of students but also help in better student self-direction and effort regulation that lead to better student experience (Bennet et al. 2020).

According to Weston et al. (2017), stress is easily encountered and can impact student motivation and performance on both academic and personal levels. To overcome this, people can utilize social resources, which include support from peers, sharing of hardships, and the exchange of aid, organizational resources, which include technical and educational resources; and personal resources, which include hobbies, passions, and practices that make them feel better about themselves. In an article entry by Güngör and Sari (2022), School burnout and its effects on motivation are a risk to students' mental health and education. Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation,

and Amotivation are three forms of motivation that should be considered and analyzed when discussing the well-being of students on the academic and personal level to ensure optimal functionality and well-being. Intrinsic Motivation is the willingness to do something considered fulfilling and pleasurable for the person, Extrinsic Motivation is the willingness to do something for external rewards, and amotivation is the loss of motivation to persist in goal-directed behavior.

In regard to educators and teaching environments, good educators can be found anywhere, but what they teach and how it is digested are unique to each student. Student motivation may considerably be affected by the figure mentoring them, including educator features and qualities and external concerns like credit given and nature of the topic or any unique difficulty found by a student which can be felt in any learning mode (Joan et al. 2009). Lou and Xu (2022) stated that positive education has profoundly affected students and promotes well-being and better learning. Motivation brought on by a sense of belongingness and a connection with peers helps improve learning quality and performance (Kotera et al., 2021). Baber (2020) also backs student interaction as a helper in student motivation due to each student's relatedness in shared struggles and the collaborative actions they experience while in the presence of one another.

Although more studies are being conducted relating to learning in both online and face-to-face classes, there are not many studies about hybrid learning, especially in our local literature. This paper aims to create a foundation that can serve in distinguishing the best mode of learning for students and to determine what the students' views are on the modes of learning and what they believe is best for them, adequate to their needs, and applicable to their situation.

This study focuses on the experiences of students during hybrid learning, which involves the challenges they have overcome, the changes they had to face, and the things they learn in experiencing this mode of learning that involves both face-to-face and online classes as well as their views regarding their learning environment and overall wellbeing as a learner.

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore students' experience and perceived advantages and disadvantages of both learning modes that are face-to-face and online learning of Psychology students in National University Fairview. Specifically, the study aims to support the following, such as describing the students' educational experiences with hybrid learning, exploring students' perspectives in reconnecting with peers, discovering the students' adjustment with a hybrid learning setting of education, knowing the students' comparative insights on new normal and pre-pandemic face-to-face classes.

Methodology

This study used qualitative design and subsequent methods to collect the data required to help understand the phenomenological experiences of students transitioning to hybrid learning. To get the appropriate and desired results, the researchers conducted a semi-structured interview and a part of it covered the research related questions.

The participants of the study are NU Fairview Psychology students from the 2nd to 3rd year levels of School Year 2022-2023 that were selected using purposive sampling, mainly nonprobability sampling with an experiential approach in phenomenological research. Said students were chosen as they have the necessary experience relevant to the study and subsequently excludes participants who are first years, in other courses, transferees, and students who have not experienced online class during the pandemic. The data was gathered through an interview composed of research related questions to gather experiences related to hybrid learning.

To begin in this endeavor, the informed consent in conducting the study was provided by the researchers, who were given approval by the Psychology Research Adviser and Psychology Research Professor. After the submission and approval of the informed consent form, the semi-structured interview was provided by the researchers and was also submitted for approval and validation by experts. After the guided interview proposals and validations, the researchers determined the participants who were qualified to participate by using purposive sampling. The study was introduced and explained to the participants meticulously, announcing its purpose and objective. After determining the qualified participants and introducing the study, the informed consent form was presented to those who were willing to participate in the study that the researchers were conducting. The interview followed immediately and when the desired number was obtained, data gathering was done and all the desired information was kept, the researchers examined, transcribed and analyzed the gathered information.

The Thematic Analysis used in analyzing data as the focus of the study is on the experience of college students in the transition from face-to-face to online class. Also, to understand and to identify the patterns or themes of the construct of the participants personal thoughts and experiences (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The Interviewer asked about collective experience and the participants shared some experiences according to the interview questionnaires. (1) After the interview, a deeper analysis was conducted by the researchers, (2) Codes were then extracted from all of the answers. The codes described the answered content. (3) The researchers generated themes based on the collected data. The codes were split up and combined in order to generate a theme which are more broader than the codes. (4) Next was reviewing the themes. The researchers return to the data and the themes that were generated from participants' answers to see if it correlates. If a problem occurs, the themes were split, combined or discarded. (5) The themes were then defined and named by what the researchers means for each of them and how they aided in understanding the data behind those themes. Lastly, (6) presenting the themes that were gathered from the Data (Caulfield, 2019). To further establish the validity of our findings, the researchers engaged in member checking and external validation. The researchers shared the preliminary thematic analysis findings with the participants and validators and sought their feedback for verification. This process allowed participants to confirm the accuracy of the interpretation

of their statements, which enhanced the credibility of our analysis.

The ethical considerations maintained in this study are the informed consent form, confidentiality, anonymity, voluntary participation, risk of sharing experiences, and research limitations. The said considerations were discussed to preclude as much harm as possible, whether physical or psychological. The researchers made sure to present an informed consent form to the participants to ensure that minimal to no harm were done during the research process. The informed consent stated the nature and purpose of the study, data gathering procedure, potential risks and benefits, incentives, permission for publication, confidentiality of data, participant's responsibilities, and voluntary agreement to take part in the study.

Results and Discussion

This section aims to elucidate and share our findings from the qualitative data gathered from participants that parallel our research questions. This involves an analysis that delves into the struggles, benefits, and challenges that students have faced with hybrid learning and education as a whole.

Table 1. *Summary of Themes*

<i>Sample Quotes</i>	<i>Sub Themes</i>	<i>Global Theme</i>
"It really depends on the person on how they view pero personally, okay naman siya sakin."	Exploration of Hybrid Learning	Accepting the Hybrid Shift
"I believe that hybrid learning is probably a new opportunity to incorporate other types or styles of learning as well as discovering ways to adapt to a new setting."		
"Pwede silang mag multi task pwede pong nag aral sila sa class while working nakikinig sila ng lecture while working"		
"mas nagkakaroon ng communication dun sa learnings namen inside the class"	Strength of the Hybrid Learning	
"The pro of hybrid classes is the flexibility it offers and the availability of various resources for research."		
"mas nag fo-focus sila sa pag play sa online like Call of Duty kaya 'di sila nakakapag focus"	Navigating The Challenge and Difficulties	Hybrid Hurdles
"The fast pacing of the curriculum in the limited time available for face-to-face classes."		
"meron mga certain schedule na kung kelan face to face lang kayo tapos meron certain schedule na online kayo dun sa isang prof medyo mahirap mag adjust..."		
"Inconsistent policy-making and adjustments in the curriculum, which may still reflect pre pandemic teaching styles."		
"meron mga factors den sa bahay na nakakaffect sa mga studyante kunware kapag bigla bigla kang inutusan or mga problem sa bahay or mga distractions..."	Extraneous Variable affecting learning	
"One negative aspect is that I had to adjust to using technologies. It was difficult for me and I often needed assistance from others."		
"Mahirap po sa akin kasi working student ako, kaya naging mahirap sa oras at pag-adjust ng pahinga o tulog."	Overcoming, Adapting and adjusting	Finding Balance
"Nakakapag-adjust na po ang mga professors sa online setup, kahit minsan mayroon pa rin na mahina ang boses."		
"The tight schedule of alternative online and onsite classes posed a challenge."		
"Challenges with the implementation of safety measures like NU Safe, leading to delays and issues with the database."	Strict Change for Safety	
"nuong bago mag pandemic walang face mask, lahat pwede mong magawa."		
"Papasok ka ng school naka face mask ka andami mo pang kailangan ipakita like nu safe ganon tapos parang doble ingat ka talaga ngayon hybrid"		
"In face-to-face classes, there is more enjoyment and increased opportunities for educator and student interactions through activities."	Interactive Socialization	Beyond the Screen
"Improved student adaptation to hybrid learning, leading to increased participation compared to the online setup."		
"In face-to-face classes, students are definitely more responsive and attentive to professors and instructors."		
"Initial connections and bonding between students and teachers through online interactions, leading to a closer relationship when transitioning to face-to-face classes."	Dynamics of Face-to-face interaction	
"nung pandemic is nagkaron ako ng anxiety pa sa pagsasalita sa harap"		
"It's definitely much better because you get to bond more. When you see them physically, you can see their smiles and their faces, creating genuine bonds."		
"Being in an onsite setting allows us to better understand the vibe and synergy among students and professors."		

Theme Description

The researchers employed an inductive coding process to gather the necessary data. All three researchers have familiarized themselves with the data through thorough and multiple readings. Initial codes were then generated to identify and capture segments of data that bring significance. Braun and Clarke also stated that the researchers have an active role, meaning that the researchers should interpret the data with their own subjective abilities and elucidations.

Through comparison, pattern-recognition, and connection the researchers have identified five discrete themes: (1) Accepting The Hybrid Shift, (2) Hybrid Hurdles, (3) Beyond the Screen, (4) Finding Balance, These themes represented the most relevant experiences of this study's participants in connection to Hybrid Learning.

Accepting The Hybrid Shift- This theme explores the various experiences of our participants in relation to hybrid learning. The theme further explores students' ability to manage face-to-face components and online components that allow them to optimally attend classes and improve their abilities and knowledge as they go on.

The theme "Accepting The Hybrid Shift" we can relate Zheng et al. 's (2021) study, which states that Online Learning can be effective with academic works and activities that are not so hands-on heavy, in our case: Psychology, and that students prefer it due the offered versatility that is attributed to its ability to have synchronous and asynchronous sessions. Student and teacher production is also made efficient due to online learning's ability to be conducted wherever, anytime, and whenever a student wants which makes it more appealing, not to mention that it also helps in aiding students in financial matters by cutting costs like transportation fares and costs for printing if they don't have a printer for themselves at home (Gautam, 2022). Online learning, which is an aspect of hybrid learning, can produce a positive learning environment for students by using methods and models like the PERMA model stated in Lou and Xu's (2022) study which had features like "Positive Emotion," "Engagement," "Relationships," "Meaning," and "Accomplishment," which are all necessary factors to ensure that students can continuously experience a seamless learning experience. Another aspect of hybrid learning students found alluring was the fact that it is convenient, especially in regards to the materials, recordings, and other resources students can access anytime, that bestows upon them autonomy and flexibility in how they wish to tackle learning (Atwa et al., 2022). On the other hand benefits viewed as effective learning offer a smooth transition from online to face-to-face and considers it as a safe mode of learning in case of another situation like a pandemic outbreak (Potra et al., 2021). In addition, standard classes promote interaction and student participation compared to online classes students have a better understanding and learning experience which helps the students learn more efficiently (Miles et al., 2018).

Hybrid Hurdles- This specific theme addresses and identifies the various struggles and difficulties that students face in both Online and Face-to-Face settings. These include a communication gap between students and professors, tedious time schedules, transportation and financial difficulties, and technical issues relating to the online setting. This theme also analyzes their difficulties in adjusting with hybrid learning in its earliest stages and how they surmounted these obstacles.

Hybrid Learning has many great upsides, but like all things made beautiful one can still find a disadvantage to it. Online Learning, an integral and innate aspect of hybrid learning, suffers from its reliance upon a stable internet connection, high performance devices, and it requires, although not explicitly stated, a good environment that allows students to thrive, which are all external factors that cannot be easily demanded, especially for families that do not have the financial capabilities, and although online learning comes with many benefits its main potential is really only utilized when one meets all the requirements necessary to adhere to it (Ouma, 2021). Online learning in hybrid learning also comes with the possibility of facing distractions like games and social media, and although Hybrid learning allows for in person and online classes students still tend to feel loneliness due to feeling isolated with the lack of in-person interaction or peers, and although teachers are present and cooperating with students, some teachers might be technologically illiterate or incapable of understanding how to best utilize these new technologies which might dampen their abilities to effectively communicate with students, also there is a possibility that online learning might cause health hazards like eyesight complications and posture problems due to hunching and leaning towards the screen (Gautam, 2022). A few more variables that play into why hybrid learning has various struggles is that due to its flexibility, students might be inclined to procrastinate which hampers their sense of urgency and blunts their motivation, peer and teacher interaction is also impeded due to the nature of it switching from Face-To-Face to Online setups which does not lead to creating and fostering a good environment for both student and teacher to thrive in (Alawamleh et al., 2020).

Furthermore, hybrid learning does increase engagement across the board which then helps in improving students' communication skills that are advantageous to them socially and academically making hybrid learning accessible to others while terminating other challenges that students may have encountered before the employment of hybrid learning (Boyarsky, 2021). Another weakness was proven in the study of Kotera et al. (2021), which compared it to another mode of learning, which is online learning. It makes students have less interaction and makes them feel separated and alone which results in various difficulties for them.

Beyond The Screen- This theme mainly highlights the importance of social interaction beyond their phones and computers. They share the value of interacting with peers and educators to produce a seamless learning experience while also bolstering the benefits of face-to-face interaction and the importance of socializing and collaborating to produce an optimal learning environment.

There are things more important than what you see in front of your screen, and that can take shape in the form of your friends, hobbies,

and family. Hybrid learning allows one the advantages of Online Learning while gradually eliminating its advantages, and with it involving the Face-To-Face setting it drives a sense of normalcy towards students while changing the setting from a more teacher-centered way to a student-centered form of learning that allows for more flexibility, autonomy, a prospering sense of responsibility, and allows for better learning experiences (Li et al., 2021). Hybrid learning also allows for more effective student interaction and collaboration that lead to desirable outcomes in the learning process while not compromising the teacher-student bond that we believe is important, Hybrid learning has also demonstrated that students are capable of self-directed and self-regulated actions with peers while still collaborating with their instructors to achieve effective and flexible learning through both face-to-face and technological means (Bennet et al., 2020).

Finding Balance- This theme highlights the adaptability and benefits of hybrid learning. It focuses on students' adaptability and flexibility with adjusting to new modes of learning. This highlights the benefits, ease of adjustment, and the struggles that new learning modes offer.

In the study of Goel (2022), It was stated that hybrid learning allows the students to learn at their own pace which is beneficial for them as it provides a personalized learning experience that develops an abundance of skills like time management which psychology students have applied to themselves during their hybrid learning experience and they also bear different perspectives for some students take it as a challenge and a learning experience, especially with their adjustment due to its flexibility and varying features. Student's motivation also helps them to adapt to the new mode of learning by utilizing various resources like social resources that are in regards to their peers and relationships, organizational resources that involve their professors and other provided materials, resources, and events provided by the institute, and personal resources that relate to their passions, hobbies, and lifestyle (Weston et al., 2017).

Conclusions

The researchers have employed Thematic Analysis to analyze and interpret the data collected, and through that the researched have identified the five key themes discussed in the previous section which are: "Welcoming The Hybrid Shift," "Hybrid Hurdles," "Beyond the Screen," "Transition of Learning Modes," and "Finding Balance." Themes that have captured students' insights and perspective on their experiences in Hybrid Learning.

This paper gathered data based on the experiences of Psychology students in hybrid learning. The themes found and analyzed involve the debate on which mode of learning is most suitable for students of all predicaments. Students recognize the advantages and disadvantages of the two modes of learning and have subsequently supported blended learning while still wary of its disadvantages and challenges. The themes further include and explores students' perceived benefits and disadvantages of the current mode of learning and the different desirable and challenging features included when considering the applicability of hybrid learning as a primary and worthwhile option for education in the near future.

The thematic analysis revealed multiple facets of the students' educational experiences with Hybrid Learning, especially through probing and initiating follow up questions. The themes called 'Accepting the Hybrid Shift', 'Finding Balance' and 'Hybrid Hurdles', has delved into the strengths, weaknesses, compromises and experiences of the students in this approach, as well as the delicate balance required for optimal performance and changes they have made once exposed to the mix of Online and Face-To-Face learning modes. All of this information was gathered and produced through delicate questions and the subsequent meticulous treatment and organization of data.

- Explore students' perspectives on reconnecting with peers

The "Beyond the Screen" theme highlighted the student's perspective on reconnecting with peers and instructors, further accentuating the value of face-to-face interaction and the benefits it brings to the overall learning experience.

- Discover the students' adjustment to a hybrid learning setting of education.

The theme of "Accepting The Hybrid Shift", "Beyond the Screen", "Hybrid Hurdles" and "Finding Balance" provided insights into the students' adjustment process, obstacles encountered, and obstacles they had overcome to adapt in the hybrid learning setting, highlighting the reliefs and challenges they faced and the need for support and adequate resources to overcome these obstacles.

- Know the students' comparative insights on the "New Normal" and pre-pandemic face-to-face classes.

The "Hybrid Hurdles", "Accepting the Hybrid Shift" themes explored students' comparative insights into the pre-pandemic and 'new normal' face-to-face teaching, providing a diversified understanding of student preferences and perspectives on different learning methods.

Overall, the findings about students' educational experiences with hybrid learning in this study have provided valuable insights into their perceptions and adjustments in this learning mode. The findings underscore the importance of supporting students in their transition, providing adequate resources, and fostering meaningful connections with peers and instructors. This study's outcomes gratify and justify the research by shedding light on the nature of hybrid learning, informing educational institutions, and educators on strategies to enhance students' experiences and optimize their learning outcomes in this learning mode.

The researchers recommend the following to further develop and improve the study. Future researchers can explore the lengthy effects of hybrid learning including factors such as student participation, performance, engagement, along with overall academic outcomes, as well as the efficiency and persistence of this learning mode in higher education. They can also conduct research to identify the most efficient instructional strategies or course design to increase student engagement or participation in a hybrid learning setting. They may also explore the faculty's perception regarding hybrid learning including the faculty's attitude, preferences, challenges as well as their satisfaction towards hybrid learning. They may also investigate the accessibility of hybrid learning, determine the impact of hybrid learning on students with diverse backgrounds including learners with disabilities and students from low-income households.

References

- Amir, L.R., Tanti, I., Maharani, D.A. et al. Student perspective of classroom and distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic in the undergraduate dental study program Universitas Indonesia. *BMC Med Educ* 20, 392 (2020). <https://bmcmededuc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-020-02312-0#citeas>
- Alawamleh, M., Al-Twait, L. M., & Al-Saht, G. R. (2020, August 24). The effect of online learning on communication between instructors and students during covid-19 pandemic. *Asian Education and Development Studies*. Retrieved January 11, 2023, from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/AEDS-06-2020-0131/full/html?s kipTracking=true>
- Atwa H, Shehata MH, Al-Ansari A, Kumar A, Jaradat A, Ahmed J, Deifalla A. Online, Face-to-Face, or Blended Learning? Faculty and Medical Students' Perceptions During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Mixed-Method Study. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2022 Feb 3;9:791352. doi:10.3389/fmed.2022.791352. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8850343/>
- Baber, H. (2020). Social interaction and effectiveness of the online learning – A moderating role of maintaining social distanc during the pandemic COVID-19. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 11(1), 159-171 <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-09-2020-0209>
- Bennett, D., Knight, E., & Rowley, J. (2020). The role of hybrid learning spaces in enhancing higher education students' employability. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 51(4), 1188–1202. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12931>
- Biwer, F. Wiradhay, W., Ebrink, M., Et al. (2021). Changes and Adaptations: How University. *Font. Psychol., Students Self-Regulate Their Online Learning During the COVID-19 Pandemic*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.642593/full>
- Boyarsky, K. (2021). The Benefits of Hybrid Learning in a Post-COVID World. <https://resources.owllabs.com/blog/hybrid-learning-benefits>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Caulfield, J. (2022, November 25). How to Do Thematic Analysis | Step-by-Step Guide & Examples. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
- Gautam, P. (2021, May 12). Advantages And Disadvantages Of Online Learning. *eLearning Industry*. <https://elearningindustry.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-online-learning>
- Gherheş V, Stoian CE, Fărcaşiu MA, Stanici M. E-Learning vs. Face-To-Face Learning: Analyzing Students' Preferences and Behaviors. *Sustainability*. 2021; 13(8):4381. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/8/4381/htm>
- Goel, G. (2022, December 2). Impact of Hybrid Learning on new and skill-based learning. *Times of India Blog*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/voices/impact-of-hybrid-learning-on-n ew-and-skill-based-learning/>
- Güngör A, Sari HI. Effects of Academic Motivation on School Burnout in Turkish College Students. *Int J Adv Couns*. 2022;44(3):414-431. doi: 10.1007/s10447-022-09477-x. Epub 2022 Jul 1. PMID: 35791378; PMCID: PMC9247920. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10447-022-09477-x?fbclid=IwAR0BuTvD>
- Joan Gorham & Diane M. Christophel (2009) Students' perceptions of teacher behaviors as motivating and demotivating factors in college classes, *Communication Quarterly*, 40:3, 239-252, DOI: 10.1080/01463379209369839
- Kotera, Y., Chircop J., Hutchinson, L., Rhodes, C., Green, P., Jones, R. M., Kaluzeviciute, G., & Garip, G. (2021). Loneliness in online students with disabilities: Qualitative investigation for experience, understanding and solutions. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 18(1), 64. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00301-x>
- Li, Q., Li, Z., & Han, J. (2021). A hybrid learning pedagogy for surmounting the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic in the performing arts education. *Education and information technologies*, 26(6), 7635–7655. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10612-1>
- Lou Jialing and Xu Qinmei (2022) The development of positive education combined with online learning: Based on theories and practices. *Front. Psychol.* 13:952784. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.952784. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.952784/full>

- Mahlaba, S. C.. (2020). Reasons why self-directed learning is important in South Africa during the Covid-19 pandemic. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 34(6), 120-136. <https://dx.doi.org/10.20853/34-6-4192>
- Miles D, Mesinga J, Zuchowski I (2018). Harnessing opportunities to enhance the distance learning experience of MSW students: An appreciative inquiry process. *Social Work Education* (37(6):705-717.<https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2018.1447557>
- Ouma, C. (2021). Online learning perception among college students during COVID-19 pandemic around the world: Review. *African Educational Research Journal*, 9(3): 790-799. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1324124.pdf>
- Potra, S., Pugna, A., & Negrea, R. (2021). Facing COVID-19 Challenges: 1st-Year Students' Experience with the Romanian Hybrid Higher Educational System. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(6), 3058. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18063058>
- Rosita, N., Saun, S., Mairi, S. (2020). Google Classroom for Hybrid Learning in Senior High School. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=hybrid+AND+learning+AND+school&id=EJ1325214>
- Study International Staff. (2020, April 4). Why online learning is better than face-to-face learning. Study International. <https://www.studyinternational.com/news/online-learning-better-face-learning/>
- Sun, Y., & Rogers, R. (2021). Development and validation of the Online Learning Self-efficacy Scale (OLSS): A structural equation modeling approach. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 35(3), 184-199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923647.2020.1831357>
- Tadesse, S. and Muluye, W. (2020) The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Education System in Developing Countries: A Review. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 8, 159-170. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=103646>
- Weston JF, Gardner D, Yeung P. Stressors and Protective Factors among Veterinary Students in New Zealand. *J Vet Med Educ*. 2017 Spring;44(1):22-28. doi: 10.3138/jvme.0116-014R1. PMID: 28206841. <https://jvme.utpjournals.press/doi/10.3138/jvme.0116-014R1>
- Zheng, W., Ma, Y.-Y., & Lin, H.-L. (2021). Research on Blended Learning in Physical Education During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Case Study of Chinese Students. *SAGE Open*, 11(4). <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/21582440211058196>
- Zheng, M. (2021, September 16). Online learning during COVID-19 produced equivalent or better student course performance as compared with pre-pandemic: empirical evidence from a school-wide comparative study - BMC Medical Education. *BioMed Central*. <https://bmcomeduc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-021-02909-z>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Christian Angelo Ruiz

National University – Philippines

Jerome Arvin Sebastian

National University – Philippines

Robert Wayne Torres

National University – Philippines

Danise Angelica G. Lacson

National University – Philippines